

Yield potential

Correlation and path analysis of rice grain yield under alkali stress conditions

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We studied direct and indirect associations of yield components with grain yield in 27 short-duration rice genotypes to identify suitable criteria for effective selection of genotypes under alkaline stress condition.

The experiment was laid out at CRS in a randomized block design during 1993 wet season (rabi) with three replications. The soil was clay loam with pH 8.6, EC

1.4 dS/m, and 18% exchangeable Na. The soil had low N (109 kg), low P (10.8 kg), and high K (672 kg). The crop received 125-50-50 kg NPK/ha during the season. We transplanted 25-d-old rice seedlings at 20- × 10-cm spacing in 2- × 3-m plots. The genotypes had 105-115 d durations and grain yield varied from 1.7 to 6.0 t/ha.

Grain yield was positively and significantly correlated with panicle length ($r = 0.578$), grains per panicle ($r = 0.547$), 100-grain weight ($r = 0.401$), dry matter production ($r = 0.901$), and straw yield ($r = 0.752$) (see table). Straw yield was positively and significantly correlated with plant height ($r = 0.523$), panicle length ($r = 0.698$), grains per panicle ($r = 0.544$), and dry matter production ($r = 0.858$). Dry matter production was significantly and

positively correlated with plant height ($r = 0.44$), panicle length ($r = 0.692$), grains per panicle ($r = 0.600$), 100-grain weight ($r = 0.410$), and root weight ($r = 0.378$).

Path analysis studies indicated that dry matter production had a high direct effect on grain yield (see table). Productive tillers per plant and grains per panicle had low direct effects. For the other traits, the effect was negative. Although panicle length, 100-grain weight, and straw yield had a positive and significant correlation with grain yield, they did not exhibit direct effect on grain yield. These characters had an indirect effect on grain yield, mainly through dry matter production.

Dry matter production seems to be the most reliable character for effective selection of genotypes under alkali stress conditions. ■

Coefficients of correlation and path analysis^a showing direct and indirect effects of yield components on grain yield under alkali stress condition. Srivilliputtur, India. 1993.

Variable		Plant height	Panicle length	Productive tillers/plant	Grains/panicle	100-grain weight	Root weight	Dry matter production	Straw yield	Grain yield
Panicle height	rg ^b	-	0.574**	-0.303	0.306	0.184	0.255	0.440*	0.523**	0.263
	P ^c	<u>-0.059</u>	-0.014	-0.029	0.015	-0.006	-0.072	0.545	-0.118	-
Panicle length	rg	-	-	-0.089	0.647**	0.139	0.298	0.692**	0.698**	0.578**
	P	-0.034	<u>-0.024</u>	-0.009	0.032	-0.005	-0.084	0.857	-0.157	-
Productive tillers/plant	rg	-	-	-	0.024	-0.215	0.180	-0.137	-0.018	-0.091
	P	0.018	0.002	<u>0.097</u>	0.001	0.007	-0.051	-0.169	0.004	-
Grains/panicle	rg	-	-	-	-	-0.188	0.352	0.600**	0.544**	0.547**
	P	-0.018	-0.016	0.002	<u>0.050</u>	0.006	-0.099	0.743	-0.122	-
100-grain weight	rg	-	-	-	-	-	-0.127	0.410*	0.291	0.401*
	P	-0.011	-0.003	-0.021	-0.010	<u>-0.032</u>	0.036	0.508	-0.066	-
Root weight	rg	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.378*	0.193	0.161
	P	-0.015	-0.007	0.017	0.018	0.004	<u>-0.281</u>	0.469	-0.043	-
Dry matter production	rg	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.858**	0.901*
	P	-0.026	-0.017	-0.013	0.030	-0.013	-0.106	<u>1.239</u>	-0.193	-
Straw yield	rg	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.752**
	P	-0.031	-0.017	-0.002	0.027	-0.009	-0.054	1.062	<u>-0.225</u>	-

^a Residual effect = 0.35; underlined figures denote direct effects. * and ** = significant at the 5 and 1% level, respectively. ^b rg = genotypic correlation coefficient. ^c P = path coefficient.

Grain quality

Milling characters of raw and parboiled popular rice cultivars

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More than half of the rice consumed in India is parboiled; in Tamil Nadu State it exceeds 85%. Raw and parboiled rices have different qualities. We investigated the differences in some milling characters between raw and parboiled rices in 15 popular cultivars.

Nine short-duration (10.5-120 d) cultivars were grown in 1992 kuruvai

season (Jun-Jul sowings) and six medium-duration (125-140 d) cultivars in 1992 thaladi season (Sep-Oct sowings). A recommended package of practices was followed for a transplanted lowland crop. Seeds were collected from replicated trials, cleaned, and dried to 14% moisture content. Samples were drawn 1 mo after harvest. One half was

parboiled by the double steaming method used in conventional rice mills and dried to 14% and the other half was raw milled. Both samples were dehulled in a laboratory model Satake rubber roll huller and milled for 30 s in a McGill miller. Milling characters were estimated (see table).

All the cultivars had decreasing mean values for brown rice percentage in parboiled rice compared with raw rice because of soaking losses. Brown rice percentage in raw rice ranged from 75.4% for Improved White Ponni to 79.5% for ADT36; in parboiled rice, it ranged from 74.5% for Improved White Ponni to 77.8% for ADT39. Quantity of hull removed in parboiled rice was less than that for raw rice. The hull percentage was 20.0-23.0% in raw rice and 19.0-21.8% in parboiled rice. The most hull (23.0%) was removed from Co 45 and Improved White Ponni in raw rice and

21.8% from Improved White Ponni in parboiled rice.

Parboiling improved the milling characters in all varieties. Milling recovery ranged from 71.3% for Improved White Ponni to 75.7% for ADT39 in raw rice compared with 72.7% for Improved White Ponni to 75.9% for ADT36 in parboiled rice. The physico-chemical structure of the kernel was altered in parboiling, conferring strength to the grains due to gelatinization by double steaming and subsequent drying.

More bran was obtained with raw milling than with parboiling, with 1.1% in ADT38 and ADT39 and 4.2% in ASD18. This suggests that uniform milling for 30 s for both raw and parboiled rice is inadequate. Time should vary for uniform polishing. In raw milling, ASD18, IR64, IR50, and ASD16 yielded 5.0-5.7% bran and IR36 yielded only 3.3%, indicating that cultivars vary

in hardness and resistance of milling. On the contrary, in parboiled rice, bran yield was highest in Co 43 (3.4%) and least in ADT37(1.4%), perhaps because of increased variation in gelatinization for the cultivars, even under similar conditions (see table).

Head rice recovery in parboiled rice was much greater than that in raw rice. The head rice recovery of the cultivars under the raw rice treatment was relatively lower than their normal averages because of the environmental conditions to which samples were exposed from harvest until analysis. Cultivars, however, may respond differently to head rice recovery because of genetics.

In both raw and parboiled rices, no definite trend was observed in brown rice, total milled rice, head rice, and hull and bran content, suggesting that genetics and the environment largely govern the characters. ■

Milling characters (%) for raw and parboiled rice of 15 popular cultivars. TNRRRI, Aduthurai, India. 1992.

Variety	Raw rice					Parboiled rice				
	Brown rice	Hull	Total milled rice	Bran	Head rice	Brown rice	Hull	Total milled rice	Bran	Head rice
IR50	77.7	21.9	72.7	5.0	50.0	76.4	20.5	74.0	2.4	71.0
TKM9	78.1	20.9	73.2	4.6	48.5	76.5	20.4	73.7	2.8	72.8
ADT37	79.0	20.5	75.1	3.9	53.5	77.3	19.4	75.6	1.4	74.5
Co 37	78.4	20.6	74.1	4.0	41.1	77.0	19.2	75.4	1.5	74.6
ADT36	79.5	20.0	74.9	4.5	46.8	77.6	19.0	75.9	1.5	73.8
IR36	79.2	20.2	75.2	3.3	52.5	77.3	19.7	75.3	2.0	74.0
IR64	77.7	22.0	72.4	5.2	46.7	77.0	21.0	73.9	2.8	71.7
ASD16	78.6	21.0	72.8	5.0	45.0	75.9	19.8	74.1	1.8	73.1
ASD18	78.5	20.6	72.6	5.7	46.9	76.9	20.1	75.3	1.6	74.0
ADT39	79.7	20.0	75.7	3.9	51.6	77.8	19.5	75.8	2.8	73.9
IR20	78.2	21.2	73.2	4.8	46.5	76.9	19.5	74.5	2.6	72.8
ADT38	78.4	21.5	74.4	3.9	52.2	77.4	20.5	74.4	2.8	72.8
Co 43	78.0	21.7	73.0	4.8	54.9	76.6	20.2	73.0	3.4	71.5
Co 45	76.5	23.0	71.6	4.7	40.8	76.5	20.7	73.8	2.7	72.2
Improved White Ponni	75.4	23.0	71.3	3.9	47.4	74.5	21.8	72.7	1.8	71.3
\bar{X}	78.2	21.2	73.5	4.5	48.3	76.8	20.1	74.4	2.7	72.9
SD	1.1	0.9	1.30	0.62	4.06	0.78	0.73	0.93	0.61	1.15

Induction of mutants with low amylose content in endosperm using a chemical mutagen, N-methyl-N-nitrosourea

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With the increasing demand for quality rice in China, we are focusing on breeding cultivars with good eating quality.

According to our recent surveys, urban people in Yunnan Province prefer soft-cooked rice with low amylose content. We studied how changes in the environment affect amylose content in the endosperm. An improved japonica cultivar, Hexi 4, was grown in Yunnan Province at five locations with different

altitudes (Table 1). Temperature during grain-filling markedly affected amylose content, with temperature below 20 °C enhancing it. Based on this finding, we are selecting elite breeding lines with lower amylose under low temperatures for high-altitude regions.

There are some traditional and improved indica cultivars with low amylose grains that are soft-cooking in Yunnan Province. We do not, however, have such japonica germplasm in the